

Application of Luminescence in the Detection of Infections in Wounds: An Emerging Diagnostic Tool, Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Pressure ulcers in the sacral region represent one of the most frequent complications in patients with prolonged immobility, being associated with high morbidity and risk of infection. The differentiation between bacterial colonization and clinically significant infection continues to be a challenge, since classical signs may be absent in chronic wounds. In this context, luminescence imaging has emerged as a non-invasive tool that allows real-time detection of bacterial load through fluorescence induced by violet light.

A case of a 68-year-old female patient with a history of cerebrovascular event and prolonged immobility is presented, who developed a sacral ulcer of approximately 25 x 25 cm, initially covered by necrotic eschar. Surgical cleaning with extensive debridement was scheduled; however, during the procedure, viable underlying granulation tissue was evidenced, so it was decided to limit the debridement. Given the suspicion of bacterial load not clinically evident, evaluation by luminescence was performed, observing green-blue fluorescence compatible with the presence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which guided management toward a targeted treatment.

The use of luminescence allowed precise identification of the distribution of bacterial load, modification of surgical conduct, and avoidance of unnecessary resection of viable tissue. This tool provides significant value in intraoperative decision-making and in the optimization of the management of complex wounds.

Luminescence is positioned as a useful complementary technology in the evaluation of pressure ulcers, allowing more precise, targeted, and real-time medicine, with potential impact on improving clinical outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Pressure ulcer, sacral ulcer, luminescence, bacterial fluorescence, chronic wounds, wound infection, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, debridement, bacterial load, non-invasive diagnosis.

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic wounds constitute a relevant public health problem due to their high incidence, impact on patient quality of life, and high costs associated with their treatment. Within this group, pressure ulcers, particularly those located in the sacral region, represent one of the most frequent entities in patients with limited mobility, chronic diseases, or prolonged hospital stays. These lesions are characterized by a deficient healing process, in which bacterial colonization and progression to infection play a determining role in clinical evolution.

The differentiation between colonization and infection in chronic wounds continues to be a diagnostic challenge in daily clinical practice. The classical signs of infection —such as erythema, pain, purulent exudate, or foul odor— may be subtle or even absent, especially in immunocompromised patients or in long-standing wounds. In this context, high bacterial load ($>10^4$ CFU/g of tissue) has been associated with delayed healing, graft and flap failure, as well as a higher risk of systemic complications, which highlights the need for more sensitive and specific diagnostic tools.

Traditionally, microbiological evaluation by culture has been the reference standard; however, it presents important limitations, such as processing time, variability in sample collection, and inability to provide real-time information. In response to these limitations, luminescence imaging has emerged as an innovative technology that allows immediate detection of bacteria in the wound through fluorescence emission induced by violet light (approximate wavelength of 405 nm). This non-invasive method provides a direct evaluation of the spatial distribution of bacterial load, facilitating clinical decision-making during patient assessment.

The basis of this technique lies in the capacity of certain microorganisms to produce fluorescent metabolites. In this sense, red fluorescence is mainly related to bacteria that synthesize porphyrins, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and other gram-positive species, while green-blue (cyan) fluorescence is characteristic of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, due to the production of compounds such as pyoverdine. On the other hand, the absence of fluorescence or the

visualization of dark tones usually indicates tissue without significant bacterial load, devitalized tissue, or areas where the fluorescent signal is not detectable. This chromatic differentiation allows not only the identification of bacteria but also the orientation of specific interventions such as targeted debridement, more precise culture sampling, and optimization of antimicrobial treatment.

The incorporation of luminescence into clinical practice has demonstrated benefits in early detection of infection, reduction of bacterial load, and improvement in healing outcomes. In addition, its use is particularly relevant in the field of plastic and reconstructive surgery, where adequate preparation of the wound bed is fundamental for the success of procedures such as skin grafts and flaps.

In this context, the case of a patient with a chronic sacral ulcer is presented, in whom luminescence imaging was used as a complementary diagnostic tool for the identification of bacterial load and the orientation of therapeutic management. The objective of this report is to describe the correlation between clinical findings and the observed fluorescence patterns, as well as to highlight the usefulness of this technology in decision-making in complex wounds.

CLINICAL CASE

This is a 68-year-old female patient with a history of prolonged immobility secondary to ischemic cerebrovascular event, also presenting type 2 diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension, who is evaluated due to a lesion in the sacral region of approximately six weeks of evolution, with progressive increase in size and deterioration of the wound bed. On physical examination, a pressure ulcer in the sacral region of approximately 25 x 25 cm in diameter is identified, with irregular borders, predominance of dry necrotic tissue of eschar type on the surface, areas of serohematic exudate, and peripheral zones with mild erythema, without evident systemic signs of inflammatory response. The lesion initially presented an aspect suggestive of extensive necrosis that conditioned the planning of surgical cleaning with aggressive debridement of devitalized tissue.

IMAGE 1: Preoperative image

IMAGE 2: Intraoperative image

During the transoperative period, after partial removal of the eschar and detailed evaluation of the wound bed, it was evidenced that a large part of the underlying tissue corresponded to viable granulation tissue, well vascularized, with adequate punctate bleeding, which motivated the decision to abort extensive debridement in order to avoid unnecessary resection of potentially recoverable tissue and preserve optimal conditions of the wound bed for future reconstruction. Given the suspicion of elevated bacterial load not clinically evident, it was decided to complement the evaluation by luminescence technique, using violet light for real-time detection of bacterial fluorescence.

IMAGE 3: Luminescence imaging assessing the presence of Pseudomonas.

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Upon evaluation, areas with intense green-blue fluorescence distributed heterogeneously over the wound bed were observed, a characteristic pattern associated with the presence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which indicated a significant bacterial load despite the absence of evident clinical signs of deep infection. This finding allowed establishing a correlation between the relatively stable macroscopic appearance of the wound and the underlying presence of relevant bacterial colonization, modifying the therapeutic conduct toward a targeted management, including selective debridement, optimization of local wound control, and adjustment of antimicrobial therapy.

The use of luminescence in this case allowed precise identification of the spatial distribution of bacterial load, avoiding both overtreatment and underestimation of the infectious component, which is particularly relevant in large complex wounds such as sacral ulcers, where preservation of viable tissue is fundamental to improve reconstructive outcomes and promote healing. This approach demonstrates the value of advanced diagnostic tools in intraoperative decision-making, allowing a more conservative, targeted, and effective management in patients with complex chronic wounds.

DISCUSSION

Pressure ulcers, particularly in the sacral region, continue to represent a relevant clinical problem in patients with prolonged immobility, with a reported prevalence that varies widely depending on the hospital setting, level of care, and patient comorbidities. Their development is directly related to sustained pressure, tissue hypoperfusion, and systemic factors such as malnutrition, diabetes mellitus, and

neurological diseases, which condition impaired healing and favor progressive bacterial colonization.

In epidemiological terms, these lesions predominantly affect hospitalized or institutionalized patients, with an incidence that may increase in intensive care units and long-stay services, as summarized in the following table:

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Variable	Reported data
Overall hospital prevalence	5–23%
Intensive care units	Up to 30%
Sacral location	60–70% of cases
Patients with limited mobility	Main risk group
Association with diabetes mellitus	Significant increase
Indirect mortality	Increased due to secondary infection

One of the main challenges in the management of these wounds is the differentiation between bacterial colonization and clinically significant infection. Bacterial loads greater than 10^4 CFU/g of tissue have been shown to interfere with healing and increase the risk of complications; however, traditional clinical evaluation is insufficient in multiple scenarios. In this context, the implementation of technologies such as luminescence has allowed better characterization of the microbiological status of the wound.

Luminescence imaging is based on the excitation of bacterial fluorophores using violet light (approximately 405 nm), generating visible emissions that allow identification of the presence and distribution of microorganisms. This technology has been developed and refined in recent decades by researchers such as Ralph DaCosta and collaborators, who contributed to the development of clinically applicable systems for wounds.

The interpretation of the colors observed through luminescence is essential for its correct clinical application, as summarized below:

Observed color	Meaning	Associated microorganisms
Red	Porphyrin production	Staphylococcus aureus, Enterococcus spp.
Green-blue (cyan)	Specific fluorophores	Pseudomonas aeruginosa
White/pale green	Viable tissue	No significant bacterial burden
Dark/black	Necrotic tissue or absence of signal	Variable
Faint yellow	Biofilm or mixed bacteria	Polymicrobial
Diffuse fluorescence	Superficial colonization	Multiple bacteria

From a microbiological perspective, the correlation between fluorescence patterns and the microorganisms most frequently involved in chronic wounds allows more precise therapeutic orientation:

Microorganism	Type	Frequency in sacral ulcers	Fluorescence
Staphylococcus aureus	Gram-positive	High	Red
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Gram-negative	High in chronic wounds	Green-blue
Escherichia coli	Gram-negative	Moderate	Variable
Enterococcus spp.	Gram-positive	Frequent	Red
Proteus spp.	Gram-negative	Moderate	Variable
Mixed flora	Polymicrobial	Very frequent	Mixed

The clinical utility of luminescence lies not only in the detection of bacteria but also in its impact on surgical decision-making, particularly in procedures such as debridement, where precise delimitation of affected tissue is crucial. In this context, comparison with traditional methods highlights its advantages:

Method	Time to result	Spatial precision	Invasive
Microbiological culture	24–72 h	Low	Yes
Clinical evaluation	Immediate	Low	No
Tissue biopsy	Variable	Moderate	Yes
Luminescence	Immediate	High	No

Furthermore, the integration of this technology into the management of complex wounds has demonstrated benefits in terms of reduction of bacterial burden, optimization of debridement, and improvement in reconstructive outcomes:

Clinical benefit	Impact
Early detection of infection	High
Guidance for selective debridement	Precise
Reduction of unnecessary antibiotics	Significant

Improvement in healing	Documented
Decrease in complications	Moderate
Support in intraoperative decision-making	High

Finally, in the present case, luminescence allowed identification of significant bacterial load by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in a wound that clinically appeared viable, modifying the initial surgical conduct and avoiding excessive debridement. This type of approach is particularly relevant in plastic and reconstructive surgery, where preservation of viable tissue is essential for the success of subsequent procedures.

Overall, current evidence supports the use of luminescence as a complementary tool of high value in the evaluation of chronic wounds, enabling more precise, targeted, and real-time medicine, representing a significant advance in the comprehensive management of patients with complex pressure ulcers.

CONCLUSION

The use of luminescence in the evaluation of chronic wounds represents an innovative diagnostic tool that allows real-time identification of bacterial load, even in the absence of evident clinical signs of infection. In the presented case, its application was decisive in modifying surgical conduct, avoiding unnecessary extensive debridement and guiding management toward a more conservative and targeted approach.

The capacity of this technology to differentiate bacterial patterns through fluorescence, particularly the detection of microorganisms such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, provides significant value in intraoperative decision-making and in the optimization of local wound treatment. This is especially relevant in the context of plastic and reconstructive surgery, where preservation of viable tissue is fundamental for the success of definitive coverage.

Overall, luminescence is positioned as a complementary tool of great utility in the comprehensive management of complex wounds, promoting more precise medicine, reducing the risk of surgical overtreatment, and contributing to better clinical outcomes. Its systematic incorporation into clinical practice could represent an important advance in the management of pressure ulcers and other chronic wounds.

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